

The Preparation of Some Heptafluoro-n- and -iso-Propyl Derivatives of Phosphorus and Silicon

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Interaction of heptafluoro-2-iodopropane and phosphorus at 220° gave bisheptafluoro-iso-propyliodophosphine and heptafluoro-iso-propyl-di-iodophosphine. No tris-heptafluoro-iso-propyl-phosphine was found. Heptafluoro-n-, and -iso-propyl derivatives of silicon have been prepared by the reaction between perfluoroalkyllithio derivative and chlorosilanes.

PERFLUOROALKYL derivatives of metals and metalloids have been studied by various investigators and have been reviewed¹. The two methods usually known for the preparation of organophosphines, (i) the interaction between the Grignard or Grignard type reagents and halophosphines, or (ii) the interaction between an alkyl halide and sodium derivative of phosphine, are not suitable for perfluoroalkyl compounds as either the perfluoroalkyl Grignards are very unstable or the perfluoroalkyl iodides are decomposed by sodium. Hence, other routes were sought.

Trifluoroiodomethane with red or white phosphorus yields various trifluoromethylphosphines².

To extend this reaction Emeleus and Smith³ have reported that heptafluoro-1-iodopropane reacts with phosphorus to give heptafluoro-n-propyliodophosphines in 65-68% yield. Mixed perfluoroalkyl and alkyl derivatives of phosphorus, arsenic and antimony have been prepared with difficulty by the exchange reaction of

perfluoroiodides with trialkyl compounds of the elements at room temperature⁴.

The objective of the present work is to extend the above reactions in an attempt to prepare perfluoroalkyl phosphines and alkyl(perfluoroalkyl)silicon compounds.

Results and Discussions

The preparative value of the reaction between perfluoroiodides and group V elements has attracted various chemists, although very little is known about the actual mechanism of these reactions. In our present work, we have found out that heptafluoro-iso-propyliodophosphines may be obtained in moderate yield from the reaction between heptafluoro-2-iodopropane and red phosphorus at 220° for about 8 hr. Optimum condition was obtained by varying the proportions of the reactants, temperature and the reaction time. The results are summarized in table 1. Although separation of the iodophosphines was difficult because of their similar volatilities, conversion of the iodophosphines to chlorophosphines by treatment with anhydrous silver chloride allows good separation because of the bigger differences in volatility. Yield of the experiment can easily be

TABLE 1—INTERACTION OF HEPTAFLUORO-2-IODOPROPANE AND PHOSPHORUS

Run	Temp in °C	(CF ₃) ₂ CFI taken in g.	Phosphine obtained in g.	(CF ₃) ₂ CFI recovered in g.	% (CF ₃) ₂ CFI recovered	% (CF ₃) ₂ CFI used	Time in h
1	198	1.519	0.028	1.305	86	14	60
2	240	8.748	0.810	4.968	57	43	48
3	218	8.600	0.291	7.859	80	20	30
4	220	21.870	0.809	19.658	90	10	12
5	220	19.582	0.924	17.494	88	12	6
6	220	7.078	0.174	6.598	93	7	4
7	220	8.111	0.172	7.650	95	5	1

increased by recycling the unreacted material as has been reported in the case of trifluoromethyl compounds.^{2a,4.}

Careful fractionation of the volatile products obtained from the reaction tube showed very small amount of phosphorus iodides. Slow trap to trap distillation *in vacuo* made it possible to obtain pure samples of the iodophosphines. The proportions of heptafluoro-iso-propyl iodophosphines were determined from the amount of heptafluoropropane obtained following alkaline hydrolysis of the iodophosphines. The yields were 60% mono-iodo- and 40% di-iodo-phosphines. No fluorocarbons were detected in this reaction, as shown by the solubility of the reaction products in aqueous alkali. Absence of fluorocarbon has also been noted with heptafluoro-n-propyl iodophosphines⁵ even at higher temperature. In the present case whilst fluorocarbons were expected, only charred products were obtained following pyrolysis of a sample heated to 350°, suggesting that the bonds between carbon and phosphorus might be strong enough to prevent breakdown of the heptafluoro-iso-propyl radical. Further, no trisheptafluoro-iso-propyl phosphine was obtained. Although the optimum yield for tris(trifluoromethyl)phosphine is obtained at 300° in the reaction of trifluoridomethane and phosphorus⁶, in the present case even at this higher temperature no tris phosphine was obtained. Probably it is unstable in the presence of excess iodine at temperatures higher than 200°. Unfortunately, the reaction between heptafluoro-2-iodopropane and phosphorus hardly takes place below 200°. The results are summarized in table 1.

The infra-red spectra of the bisheptafluoro-iso-propyl and heptafluoro-iso-propyl iodophosphines are almost identical. The P-I stretch vibration absorption band falls outside rock-salt region. It is observed that the phosphines have 3-5 strong peaks between 1350 and 1000 cm⁻¹, the positions of which do not vary significantly. Assignments of the various bands are made as follows : 1299-1120 cm⁻¹ for C-F stretching, 1000-960 cm⁻¹ for CF₃-CF deformations and 760-715 cm⁻¹ for CF₃ deformations. These values are similar to those in silyl compounds.

Perfluoroalkyl-lithium and -magnesium derivatives have been made, but are of limited use due to low yields in the coupling reactions with metal or metalloidal halides at temperatures above ambient. According to Clark et. al.⁶, heptafluoro-n-propyllithium has a transitory existence in donor solvents, and is best prepared *in situ* :

where R=alkyl or aryl, M=metal or metalloidal, x=normal valency of M.

Heptafluoro-n-propyllithium has also been made by the exchange reaction between heptafluoro-1-iodopropane and an alkyl lithium⁶. This method however

gives low yields for the preparation of organometallic or -metalloidal derivatives, due to competitive reactions of the alkyl lithium with the organometallic or -metalloidal halide. If sufficient time is allowed to form the perfluoroalkyllithium compounds first, and these are then coupled with the organo-metallic or -metalloidal halide, the lithium derivatives decompose to a considerable extent, as has been observed in the case of butyllithium and heptafluoro-2-iodopropane⁷. A further disadvantage in this case is that the other product, butyl iodide, is a liquid, whose volatility is close to that of many perfluoroalkyl-phosphines and -silanes. We have tried to extend the reaction between the perfluoroalkyl iodide and lithium metal dispersed in hexane, and obtained 70% yield of heptafluoro-n-propyl- and -isopropyl-lithium compounds. Dispersion of lithium metal (~100μ) was performed very easily as per Coates et. al.⁸ This is indeed a very convenient method, as the lithium floats in hexane, and metal can easily be scooped out in flasks filled with nitrogen, weighed and the trace of hexane is pumped out. The other product of the reaction, lithium iodide, being a solid, poses no problem of separation and does not interfere in most of the subsequent reactions. The lithio derivative so prepared were successfully coupled with alkylchlorosilanes and perfluoroalkylchlorophosphines to give mixed alkyl-perfluoroalkyl compounds of silicon and phosphorus.

Heptafluoro-n-propyltrimethylsilane⁹ and heptafluoroisopropyltrimethylsilane⁷ have previously been reported but yields were very poor (6-7%). By performing the *in situ* reaction of the iodide, lithium and chlorosilanes, we obtained about 60% yield. The only limitation is that in the case of the reaction of dimethyldichlorosilane with heptafluoropropyllithio derivatives in 1:2 molar ratio, only the mono substituted product was obtained. In the case of the iso-propyl derivative steric hindrance at silicon may be important¹⁰, although bis-n-propyl compound has previously been reported¹¹ but in very poor yield.

With mixed alkyl-perfluoroalkyl compounds of silicon and phosphorus it will indeed be very interesting to study the mode of cleavage of the alkyl and perfluoroalkyl groups from the silicon and phosphorus atom. It would also be very interesting to study the coupling in the ¹⁹F NMR spectra of the asymmetric perfluoroalkylphosphines.

In the reaction of heptafluoro-isopropylbistrifluoromethylphosphine with 1 equivalent of alkali, both trifluoromethyl groups were cleaved to give trifluoromethane[CF₃H], and sodium heptafluoro-isopropylphosphonite [C₃F₇PH(O)ONa] in quantitative yields. This preliminary result indicates that trifluoromethyl groups are more easily cleaved than heptafluoro-isopropyl groups from phosphorus. A similar result is expected from the silanes.

Experimental

As most of the materials handled in this work were sensitive to air and/or moisture, they were manipulated

in pyrex glass high vacuum system of conventional design. Reactions were usually carried out in an

apparatus connected to vacuum line via a removable trap with constant stirring at low temperature effected magnetically when necessary. Reactions were also studied in sealed pyrex tubes which, following reaction, were connected to the vacuum line using flexible rubber tubing. Compounds containing impurities of similar volatility were distilled in a special micro low temperature unit attached to the system (Fig. 1). Trap to trap separations and low temperature reactions were effected either by slush baths or IMS/dry ice bath.

Fig. 1. Low Temperature Reflux Condenser

Molecular weights were determined from vapour pressures. Perfluoroalkyl compounds were analyzed by alkaline hydrolysis in sealed tubes and quantitative collection of the fluoroalkane in the vacuum system. Halogens were determined by Volhard's method. Infra red spectra were recorded at 1-5 mm in a 100 mm cell with rock-salt window.

Iodine pentafluoride and hexafluoro propene were obtained from the Peninsular Chemical Research Inc., Florida, U.S.A.

(1) *Heptafluoro-2-iodopropane* [(CF₃)₂CFI]

Iodine pentafluoride (50.0 m.moles ; 11.10g), iodine (dried over P₂O₅) (100.0 m.moles ; 25.40g) and hexafluoro propene (250.0 m.moles ; 37.50g) were heated at 150° for 24 h in a nitrogen flushed 500 cm³ stainless steel autoclave. The autoclave was cooled to -196° and the volatile products were distilled through -78° and -196° traps. Heptafluoro-2-iodopropane (240.0 m.moles ; 73.10g) was condensed at -78°. Its purity was checked by its vapour pressure (157 mm at 0°) and IR spectra, which are in agreement with the literature value^{1,2}. MW 296.

(2) *Bisheptafluoro-isopropylido- and heptafluoro-isopropylido-iodo-phosphine* [(iso-C₃F₇)₂PI] and [iso-C₃F₇PI₂]

Red phosphorus (washed with dilute sodium hydroxide solution and distilled water and dried over P₂O₅),

TABLE 2—ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS
% Found

Compound	% Found						% Calculated					
	C	H	F	Cl	I	P/Si	H	H	F	Cl	I	P/Si
(iso-C ₃ F ₇) ₂ PI	14.2	—	53.6	—	25.3	6.1	14.5	—	53.8	—	25.5	6.2
iso-C ₃ F ₇ PI ₂	7.7	—	29.2	—	55.7	6.8	7.9	—	29.4	—	55.9	6.8
(iso-C ₃ F ₇) ₂ PCI	17.7	—	65.4	8.6	—	7.6	17.8	—	65.6	8.8	—	7.7
iso-C ₃ F ₇ PCI ₂	13.3	—	49.0	26.0	—	11.2	13.3	—	49.1	26.2	—	11.4
n-C ₃ F ₇ SiMe ₂	29.4	3.9	54.6	—	—	11.4	29.8	3.7	54.9	—	—	11.6
n-C ₃ F ₇ Si(Cl)Me ₂	22.8	2.3	50.3	13.4	—	10.5	22.8	2.3	50.6	13.5	—	10.7
iso-C ₃ F ₇ SiMe ₂	29.6	3.6	54.7	—	—	11.5	29.8	3.7	54.9	—	—	11.6
iso-C ₃ F ₇ Si(Cl)Me ₂	22.7	2.2	50.0	13.3	—	10.4	22.9	2.3	50.6	13.5	—	10.7
iso-C ₃ F ₇ P(CF ₃) ₂	17.5	—	73.0	—	—	9.1	17.7	—	73.1	—	—	9.2
iso-C ₃ F ₇ PH(O)ONa.2H ₂ O	8.5	1.2	62.3	—	—	7.0	8.5	1.2	62.5	—	—	7.1

TABLE 3—INFRA RED SPECTRA

iso-C ₃ F ₇ I (1mm)	1285 (vs) 1250 (vs) 1180 (m) 1122 (s) 960 (s) 905 (s) 750 (m,sh) 715 (w) cm ⁻¹
iso-C ₃ F ₇ H (1mm)	2980 (w) 1400 (m) 1380 (m) 1310 (vs) 1285 (m,sh) 1248 (vs) 1225 (vs) 1190 (w,sh) 910 (m, triplet) 865 (w) 745 (m) 695 (m, triplet) cm ⁻¹ .
(iso-C ₃ F ₇) ₂ PI (1mm)	2370 (w) 1760 (w) 1390 (w) 1292 (vs) 1240 (vs) 1190 (w) 985 (m) 932 (w) 852 (w) 820 (w) 755 (m) 702 (m) cm ⁻¹ .
iso-C ₃ F ₇ PI ₂ (1mm)	1400 (w) 1290 (w) 1280 (vs) 1240 (vs) 1165 (w) 1148 (w) 1090 (w) 990 (w) 960 (m) 925 (m) 815 (w) 750 (m) 715 (w) cm ⁻¹ .
(iso-C ₃ F ₇) ₂ PCL (1mm)	2360 (w) 1765 (w) 1390 (w) 1285 (vs) 1240 (vs) 1185 (w) 1160 (m) 1125 (m) 990 (m) 932 (w) 852 (w) 815 (w) 745 (m) 710 (m) cm ⁻¹ .
iso-C ₃ F ₇ PCL ₂ (1mm)	1410 (w) 1285 (m) 1280 (vs) 1235 (vs) 1170 (m) 1145 (w) 1090 (w) 980 (w) 955 (w) 930 (m) 810 (m) 750 (m) 720 (m) cm ⁻¹ .
n-C ₃ F ₇ SiMe ₃ (2mm)	2960 (m) 2910 (w) 2850 (w) 1348 (m) 1260 (vs) 1235 (vs) 1215 (vs) 1175 (m) 1130 (m) 1105 (s) 1068 (s) 1045 (w) 955 (w) 925 (w) 880 (w) 855 (s) 830 (m) 765 (m) 740 (m) 660 (w) cm ⁻¹ .
n-C ₃ F ₇ Si(Cl)Me ₃ (2mm)	2985 (m) 2915 (w) 2850 (m) 1350 (m) 1265 (vs) 1235 (vs) 1215 (vs) 1176 (m) 1128 (m) 1100 (s) 1068 (s) 1045 (w) 955 (w) 925 (w) 882 (w) 850 (s) 830 (m) 765 (m) 740 (m) 662 (w) cm ⁻¹ .
iso-C ₃ F ₇ SiMe ₃ (2mm)	2980 (w) 2960 (m) 2900 (w) 1890 (w) 1370 (w) 1285 (vs) 1260 (vs) 1170 (m) 1150 (m,sh) 1070 (s) 950 (m) 850 (s) 750 (m) 740 (m, broad) 705 (m,sh) 60 (w) cm ⁻¹ .
iso-C ₃ F ₇ Si(Cl)Me ₃ (2mm)	2965 (m) 2910 (w) 1680 (w) 1368 (w) 1280 (vs) 1265 (vs) 1225 (vs) 1175 (w) 1145 (m) 1075 (s) 950 (m) 855 (s) 750 (m) 740 (m, broad) 715 (m,sh) 635 (w) cm ⁻¹ .
iso-C ₃ F ₇ P(CF ₃) ₂ (1mm)	1380 (w) 1280 (vs) 1248 (vs) 1235 (vs) 1215 (vs) 1165 (vs) 1130 (vs) 1105 (vs) 1065 (w) 955 (s) 905 (s) 820 (w) 750 (m) 715 (m) cm ⁻¹ .
CF ₃ H/iso-C ₃ F ₇ H (3mm)	3020 (w) 2980 (w) 2260 (w) 1400 (m) 1380 (m) 1320 (m) 1310 (s) 1285 (s) 1260 (vs) 1245 (vs) 1225 (s,sh) 1205 (m) 1190 (w) 1180 (m) 1150 (vs) 1030 (s,sh) 910 (m, triplet) 740 (m, triplet) 705 (w) 695 (m, triplet) 610 (m, triplet) 520 (w, broad) 500 (w) cm ⁻¹ .

was placed in an evacuated ampoule and the required amount of heptafluoro-2-iodopropane was introduced. The ampoule was sealed and heated for a period of 1 to 60 h at 198° to 240°. The ampoule was cooled and the volatile products were separated in the vacuum system. When most of the unreacted iodo propene has been removed, the ampoule was placed in a hot water bath (ca. 80°) and the products were pumped through traps at -46°, -78° and -196°. The iodophosphines were collected in the trap cooled to -46°. Results are given in table 1. The yellow liquid produced, darkens on standing at room temperature.

Autoclave reaction

Red phosphorus (25.0g) and heptafluoro-2-iodopropane (ca. 50.0g) were reacted at 220° for 8 h in a 300 cm³ stainless steel autoclave under nitrogen atmosphere. The autoclave was cooled to -196° and then slowly allowed to warm up, while the volatile products were pumped *in vacuo* through the traps at -46°, -78° and -196°. The fractions collected at -46° was observed to contain at least two fractions, a yellow liquid and a solid at this temperature. A very slow trap to trap separation through traps at -12° (ice/salt), and -46° was carried out. Most of the previously observed solid compound was trapped at -12°. The fraction collected at -46° was again distilled through traps at -23° and -46°. The remaining less volatile compound stopped at -23°, which was identified as the di-iodophosphine and the pure mono-iodophosphine was obtained from the trap at -46°. The purity of the iodophosphines was established by their alkaline hydrolysis, i.e., from the amount of heptafluoropropane produced as follows :

(a) Bisheptafluoro-isopropylidiodophosphine (0.348m. moles ; 0.172g) was sealed in an ampoule with 5 cm³ sodium hydroxide solution (15% aq.) and kept overnight at room temperature. On opening the ampoule, volatile material was collected in the vacuum line at -196°, and was characterized as heptafluoro-isopropane [(CF₃)₂CFH] (0.667m. moles ; 0.116g), MW 171 (calcd. : 170).

(b) Heptafluoro-isopropylid-iodophosphine (0.638m. moles ; 0.289g) similarly gave heptafluoro-isopropane [(CF₃)₂CFH] (0.633m. moles ; 0.108g) (Found C₃F₇, 36.0 ; I, 56.0 ; calcd. : C₃F₇H, C₃F₇, 37.2 ; I, 55.9%).

The mixture gave (i) 70% bisheptafluoro-isopropylid-iodophosphine, bp. 138°, MW 495 (calcd. 495.87), and (ii) 30% heptafluoro-isopropyl-di-iodophosphine, bp. 195°. MW 452 (calcd. 453.77).

(3) Bisheptafluoro-isopropylchlorophosphine [(iso-C₃F₇)₂ PCI]

Bisheptafluoro-isopropylchlorophosphine (20.0 m. moles ; 9.92g) and silver chloride (15.0g) were sealed in an ampoule and kept in the dark for 7 days. On opening the ampoule *in vacuo*, the volatile products were fractionated. Bisheptafluoro-isopropylchlorophosphine, a colourless liquid, was obtained in almost quantitative

yield (8.0g ; ca. 99%), bp. 116°, MW 404 (calcd. 404.5').

(4) Heptafluoro-isopropylidichlorophosphine [iso-C₃F₇ PCI₂]

Heptafluoro-isopropylid-iodophosphine (20.0m. moles ; 9.08g) and silver chloride (15.0g) were treated as in (3). The product was obtained, in almost quantitative yield, as a colourless liquid (5.38g ; ca. 99%). bp. 88°, MW 272 (calcd. : 270.87).

(5) Heptafluoro-n-propyltrimethylsilane [n-C₃F₇ SiMe₃]

Heptafluoro-1-iodopropane (38.9m. moles ; 11.5g) was distilled in a flask containing diethyl ether 15.0cm³; Na-dry, and lithium (100μ) (1.0g ; large excess). The reaction started as soon as the mixture melted. The mixture was again cooled to -196° and trimethylchlorosilane (40.2m. moles ; 4.4g) was condensed in. The reaction mixture was maintained at -78° for about ½h, and then at -50° for 2h. Finally it was stirred at room temperature for 2 h to destroy any unreacted heptafluoro-1-lithiopropene. The products were distilled through 78° and 196° traps, while the reaction mixture was maintained at 46° to separate the majority of the volatile compounds. The remaining mixture was distilled through -23°, -46°, -78° and -196°. The fraction trapped at -46° was purified by pumping through the same traps several times, until the vapour pressure was constant. The product was obtained in 60% yield. bp. 90° ; n_D²⁰ 1.3250 [lit. ¹⁰bp. 88° ; n_D²⁵ 1.3222], MW 242 (calcd. 242).

(6) Heptafluoro-n-propyldimethylchlorosilane [n-C₃F₇ Si(Cl)Me₂]

Heptafluoro-1-iodopropane (15.4m. moles ; 4.5g), lithium (100 μ) (0.03g-atom ; 0.15g) and dimethylchlorosilane (7.4m. moles ; 0.95g) were reacted together as in (5). The reaction mixture, on trap to trap separation, as above, afforded a colourless liquid, identified as heptafluoro-n-propyldimethylchlorosilane (1.2g ; 65% based on Me₂SiCl₂ used), bp. 95° ; n_D²⁵ 1.3167 ; MW 262 (calcd. 262.5).

(7) Heptafluoro-isopropylolithium [(CF₃)₂CFLi]

Heptafluoro-2-iodopropane (9.5m. moles ; 2.81g) and lithium (100 μ) (0.06g-atom ; 0.40 g) were kept stirred in ether (15 cm³ ; Na-dry) at -50° for 4 hr. and then allowed to warm upto room temperature and kept stirred for 6 hr. at this temperature to decompose the lithio derivative to hexafluoro-propene [CF₃CF=CF₂]. The volatile products were distilled through -78°, -97° and -196°, keeping the reaction vessel at -46°. The reaction trapped at -196° was found to be a colourless gas (6.7m. moles ; 1.01g ; 71%) and was characterized as hexafluoropropane. MW 150 (calcd. 150).

(8) Heptafluoro-isopropyltrimethylsilane [iso-C₃F₇-SiMe₃]

Heptafluoro-2-iodopropane (25.3m. moles ; 7.49g), lithium (100μ) (0.07g-atom ; 0.50g) and trimethylchlorosilane (25.3m. moles ; 2.74g) were reacted together in

ether (15cm³ ; Na-dry) at-50° for 4 h same as in (5). Trap to trap separation of the products gave the title compound, as a colourless liquid (3.42g ; 55%), bp. 98° ; n_D²⁵ 1.3395 [lit.¹¹ bp. 95° ; ; n_D²⁰ 1.3384. MW 242 (calcd. 242).

(9) *Heptafluoro-isopropyl dimethylchlorosilane* [iso-C₃F₇Si(Cl)Me₂]

Heptafluoro-2-iodopropane (20.0m moles ; 5.92g), lithium (100μ) (0.03g-atom ; 0.15g) and dimethyldichlorosilane (10.0m. moles ; 1.30g) were reacted in ether (15cm³ ; Na-dry) as in (5). The reaction mixture was fractionated to give a clear liquid, identified as heptafluoroisopropyl dimethylchlorosilane (1.30g ; 50%), bp. 110° ; n_D²⁵ 1.3210. MW 262 (calcd. 262.5).

(10) *Heptafluoro-isopropyl bistrifluoromethylphosphine* [iso-C₃F₇P(CF₃)₂]

Heptafluoro-a-iodopropane (15.5m.moles ; 4.60g), lithium (100μ) (0.05g-atom ; 0.35g) and bistrifluoromethylchlorophosphine (16.0m.moles ; 3.08g) were reacted together in ether (15cm³ ; Na-dry) as described in (5). Volatile products were distilled through-78° and-196° keeping the reaction flask at-46°. The portion at-46° was distilled several times through -23°, -46°, -78° and -196° until the vapour pressure of the fraction trapped at -46° was found to be constant. Heptafluoroisopropyl bistrifluoromethylphosphine (3.10g ; 60%), bp. 88°, was obtained as clear liquid. MW 338 (calcd. 338).

(11) *Hydrolysis of heptafluoro-isopropyl bistrifluoromethylphosphine*

(a) Heptafluoro-isopropyl bistrifluoromethylphosphine (0.558m moles ; 0.19g) was sealed with 5cm³ sodium hydroxide (20% aq. solution) and kept for 6 h at room temperature. Fractionation of the volatile products gave 2:1 mixture of trifluoromethane and hexafluoropropane (1.66 m.moles ; 99%) MW 101 (calcd. for 2 CF₃H. C₃F₇H, 103).

(b) Heptafluoro-isopropyl bistrifluoromethylphosphine (0.60m.moles ; 0.20g) was shaken in a sealed tube with

sodium hydroxide (0.60m.moles ; 2.4cm³ of 10% aq. solution) at room temperature and gave trifluoromethane (1.12m.moles ; 0.074g) characterized by its IR spectra. The white solid obtained, when the aqueous solution was freeze dried for 2 days, was characterized as sodium heptafluoro-isopropylphosphinite. [C₃F₇PH(O)ONa.2H₂O].

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